

interaction appears to constitute a primary rate determining step. The zero-order kinetics in hexacyanoferrate(III) clearly suggests its involvement in a fast step only. The reaction pathways are given below

where $\text{S} = \text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$ or $\text{CH}_2 = \text{CHCOO}^-$

where $\text{S}^+ = \text{CH}_3\overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}(\text{OH})\text{COO}^-$ or $\text{CH}_2 = \overset{\oplus}{\text{C}}\text{COO}^-$

The proposed mechanism involves the formation of an intermediate species in step (I) between Ru(III) species and anion of the substrate with possible exchange of a hydroxide ion coordinated to the central metal ion. The species thus formed undergoes disproportionation yielding the carbonium radical via the hydride ion abstraction from the α -carbon atom of substrate ion by Ru(III) species. The metal hydride then undergoes rapid oxidation by hexacyanoferrate(III) ion in the subsequent step yielding initial Ru(III) species. The carbonium radical thus produced in the system will react rapidly with the hydroxyl ion producing keto acid and formic acid in oxidation of lactic acid and acrylic acid, respectively.

Applying steady state treatment to the intermediate species $[\text{Ru}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{6-x}(\text{OH})_{x-1}.\text{S}]^{(4-x)+}$ and making the reasonable assumption that $k_2 + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-] \gg k_1[\text{S}]$, the following limiting rate law is obtained.

$$\frac{-d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-}}{dt} = \frac{nk_1k_2[\text{Ru(III)}][\text{substrate}]}{k_2 + k_{-1}[\text{OH}^-]} \quad \text{... (4)}$$

where n is the number of moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) consumed in oxidation of molar [substrate]. Eqn. (4) is in complete agreement with the experimental results and thus supports the mechanism.

The independent nature of reaction rate on the ionic strength of the medium and the values of energy and entropy of activation also conform to the rate controlling step (I). The retarding trend due to $[\text{OH}^-]$ is also obvious from the rate law (4).

The proposed mechanism involves hydride ion transfer from α -carbon atom of substrate to Ru(III) species resulting in the metal hydride. This has been confirmed by examining the oxidation of tertiary butanol for more than 10 hr. Tertiary butanol having no α -carbon atom was not oxidised. This clearly offers an evidence in favour of involvement of hydrogen atom attached to the α -carbon atom of both the substrates.

In the proposed mechanism, the rate controlling step (I) involves interaction between oppositely charged ions and thus should correspond to a negative primary salt effect. However, addition of salt will involve an increase in the concentration of substrate and consequently a positive secondary salt effect. If both primary and secondary salt effects are determined by charge alone, there should be no net salt effect⁶. The salt effect observed in our case is consistent with this interpretation.

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Studies on the Adsorption and Salt Tolerance of Rosin Sulpho Sodium Oleates at Liquid/Liquid Interface

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INTERFACIAL tension parameters are responsible for enhanced oil recovery by surfactant flooding. It has been established¹⁻³ that for successful enhanced oil recovery the interfacial tension should be of the order of 10^{-3} dynes/cm. In view of this, petroleum sulphonates⁴⁻⁸ and their formulations⁹ have been used to achieve ultra low interfacial tension and several patents¹⁰⁻¹⁴ exist for their use in oil recovery. It was, therefore, thought worthwhile

to prepare soaps of sulphonated derivatives of rosin and study their interfacial tension at various liquids, such as kerosene, turpentine, benzene, toluene, *n*-hexane, octane, carbon tetrachloride, and water interface. The salt tolerance of these surfactants has also been measured.

Experimental

Rosin sulpho sodium oleate was obtained by taking rosin, graded as WG-1320, WG-1364 and WG-1400 (obtained from Rosin and Turpentine Factory, Tilwara, Garhwal). The samples were dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄ (sp. gr. 1.89) containing 8% SO₃ and suitable amounts of oleic acid and NaOH were added. All chemicals used were of B.D.H., AR grade. Sulphonated rosin, oleic acid and NaOH thus gave three samples graded as RSSO-1320, RSSO-1364 and RSSO-1400.

Measurement of interfacial tension : 2% solutions of RSSO-1320, RSSO-1364 and RSSO-1400 were equilibrated with various liquids such as kerosene, turpentine, benzene, toluene, *n*-hexane, octane, carbon tetrachloride. Interfacial tension was then measured by counting the drops¹⁵ of equilibrated samples of surfactants in the above liquids. The following expression was employed to calculate the interfacial tension :

$$Y^{ow} = \frac{V(d_1 - d_2)g}{2\pi r f (r/v^{1/3})}$$

where Y^{ow} is the interfacial tension, V the volume of a single drop, d₁ and d₂ the densities of respective phases, g the gravity, r the radius of the dropping tip and f (r/v^{1/3}) the correction factor¹⁶.

The effect of emulsifier concentration has been measured at water/benzene interface by adding RSSO-1320, RSSO-1364 and RSSO-1400 in different percentages viz., 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0 and 4.0%. The influence of various salts has also been examined at 2% surfactant solution/benzene interface with NaCl, KBr, KNO₃, K₂SO₄, KHPO₄, K₂C₂O₄ and KSCN to check the salt tolerance of these rosin sulpho sodium oleates. All the observations were carried out at 25° and the results are presented in Tables 1-4.

TABLE 1

Temp. 25 ± 1° Liquid	Surfactant concentration 2%		
	Interfacial tension dynes/cm		
	RSSO-1320	RSSO-1364	RSSO-1400
Kerosene	0.881	0.846	0.295
Turpentine	0.152	0.108	0.095
Benzene	0.539	0.527	0.501
Toluene	0.420	0.401	0.395
<i>n</i> -Hexane	0.315	0.240	0.215
Octane	0.199	0.176	0.098
Carbon tetrachloride	1.250	1.085	0.987

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	Temp. 25 ± 1° Surfactant concentration	Interface Benzene/water Interfacial tension dynes/cm		
		RSSO-1320	RSSO-1364	RSSO-1400
		1.	0.1	25.210
2.	0.2	20.051	19.706	19.231
3.	0.4	9.421	8.645	8.314
4.	0.8	3.513	2.539	2.176
5.	1.5	1.071	0.914	0.805
6.	2.0	0.539	0.527	0.501
7.	3.0	0.430	0.415	0.405
8.	4.0	0.401	0.395	0.382

TABLE 3—OPTIMUM SALT CONCENTRATIONS OF SURFACTANTS AT 25 ± 1°

Sl. No.	Salt	Optimum salt concentrations		
		RSSO-1320	RSSO-1364	RSSO-1400
1.	NaCl	1	4	0.3
2.	KBr	4	2	2
3.	K ₂ SO ₄	4	4	0.5
4.	K ₂ HPO ₄	3	4	0.2
5.	KSCN	4	3	0.1
6.	K ₂ CO ₃	4	4	4
7.	KNO ₃	4	4	3
8.	K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	3	4	0.3

TABLE 4—2% SURFACTANT SOLUTIONS/BENZENE INTERFACIAL TENSION AT OPTIMUM SALT CONCENTRATIONS AT 25 ± 1°

Sl. No.	Salt	Interfacial tension dynes/cm		
		RSSO-1320	RSSO-1364	RSSO-1400
1.	NaCl	0.0705	0.0615	0.0501
2.	KBr	0.0479	0.0701	0.0900
3.	K ₂ SO ₄	0.0701	0.0915	0.0688
4.	K ₂ HPO ₄	0.0787	0.0563	0.0817
5.	KSCN	0.0482	0.0482	0.0396
6.	K ₂ CO ₃	0.0095	0.0039	0.0187
7.	KNO ₃	0.0930	0.0314	0.0900
8.	K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	0.1270	0.0959	0.4820

Results and Discussion

The data presented in Table 1 show the interfacial tensions of RSSO-1320, RSSO-1364 and RSSO-1400 (2% solution) against kerosene, turpentine, toluene, *n*-hexane, octane and carbon tetrachloride. Octane has the lowest interfacial tension while carbon tetrachloride the highest. A comparison of the values suggests that the interfacial tensions are in some way related to the following factors :

- (i) The number of carbon atoms in the molecule (cyclic/acyclic).
- (ii) Hydrogen bonding and unsaturation.
- (iii) Number of hydrogen atoms.

Thus, in the case of turpentine, octane, *n*-hexane and kerosene, where carbon atoms range from 6-10 and hydrogen atoms range from 10-20, the interfacial tension is relatively low. Further, the high unsaturation of turpentine also appears to play an

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important part in the variation of interfacial tension. While for benzene and toluene having 6 and 7 carbon atoms, respectively with hydrogen and no hydrogen atom, the value is again very high. In case of crude petroleum which is a mixture of relatively higher hydrocarbons the type of surfactants mentioned above may act as efficient emulsifiers for enhanced oil recovery.

Table 2 depicts the interfacial tension of varying concentrations of surfactants against benzene. By plotting the data, it has been observed that as the concentration of surfactants increases, the interfacial tension decreases sharply and the change becomes linear at 2% of the surfactant solution.

Tables 3 and 4 present the data of salt tolerance of the surfactants. It is concluded from the data that surfactant solution/benzene interfacial tension first shows a lowering, but beyond a particular concentration of the salt the tension starts increasing. The optimum concentration of the salts to these surfactants and interfacial tension data depicts that K_2CO_3 favours maximum lowering of interfacial tension while $K_2C_2O_4$ the least. This may be due to the fact that interfacial packing of the absorbed monomers increases in presence of electrolytes causing a reduction in the electrostatic repulsive forces between the charged heads in the aqueous phase adjacent to the interface. The experimental results are in good agreement with the earlier work¹⁷.

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Studies of Turpentine/Water Emulsions Stabilized by Binary Mixtures of Indian Gums and Rosin

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OIL/WATER emulsions have been prepared by employing surfactants¹⁻³, gums^{4,5}, rosin soaps⁶ and finely divided solids⁷. Their physical properties i.e., stability⁸, demulsification⁹, interfacial tension¹⁰, effect of salinity on interfacial tension¹¹, viscosity¹², particle size distribution¹³, phase inversion¹⁴ and conductance¹⁵ have been cited in the literature. But no attempt has yet been made to prepare turpentine/water emulsions, by using mixtures of rosin and Indian gums as emulsifiers, which have great importance in paint industry. In view of this, it was thought worthwhile to undertake a systematic study of physical properties of turpentine/water emulsions stabilized by rosin-gum mixtures and to evaluate their relative emulsifier efficiency.

Experimental

Double distilled water (conductance 1×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and turpentine (sp. gr. 0.8745) were used in all the experiments. The rosin used was of grade WG 1320-21, provided by Rosin and Turpentine Factory, Tilwara, Garhwal. The gums used were *Khair* (*Acacia catechu*), *Sahjan* (*Moringa pterygosperma*), *Ghatty* (*Anogeissus latifolia*), *Karaya* (*Sterulia ureus*) and *Modal* (*Lannea grandis*) and were provided by the Forest Research Institute, Dehra Dun. They were purified by the method of Ingle and Bhide¹⁶. Three sets of emulsions, as described below, were prepared by agent-in-water method¹⁷, using turpentine as the internal and water as the external phase.

1. The oil phase containing 0.5% rosin added to 0.5% aqueous solution of various gums viz., *Khair*, *Ghatty*, *Sahjan*, *Karaya* and *Modal*, respectively, keeping the oil/water ratio 1 : 3.
2. The oil phase containing 0.5% rosin and the aqueous phase having 0.5% *Khair* gum mixed in different phase volume ratio viz., 1 : 9, 2 : 8, 3 : 7, 4 : 6 and 5 : 5, respectively, the samples being homogenized by Redimix mixer.